

jrefm&myawmft rnfsmavlvmcsuf

aq&q&bef*

pmwrf t uof

jrefmvr&wll usi fyav&bnh ½&myawmft rnfsm; \ obmOES h orll f jzppOf tusOf, ull
½S fvi fwi fyxm; onV yawmft rnf tpm; rsm; ull cjc m; jybVOf teuft "y&h, ES h
, Ob&sr&axmi fwl rS avlv m qet ppxm; onV yawmft rnf tac: ta0: rsm; \pum; v&
z&nf yll tajccf teuft "y&h, f ou&muritr& rnf ES h , Ob&sr&emuc h rsm; ull
qubyavlv mwi fyxm; ygonV

aon&u&og [n&rsm - ½&myawmft , Ob&sr& pum; v&zx& teuf t "y&h, ?
teuf&? *, ufteuf *P&njyteuf

edget

ppmwrf onf j jrefm&myawmft rnfsm; avlv mcsuf } pmwrf jzpjy& ½&myawmft usi fy&ll
orll faemuc h rsm; ull tajcjy&avlv m wi fyxm; ygonV x&ob&avlv m&mwV&f
½&myawmft rnf tac: ta0: rsm; ull pum; v&zx& axmi rS cjc r f p&vjzm avlv m o&h; rnf
jzplonV

jrefmvr&wll onf wplq, ES& molywv& ½&myawmft rnfsm; usi fyav&lygonV
½&myawmft ES h quby&eonh pmay? orll f ES h , Ob&sr&emuc h rnf rnf uvnf
p&vDi± z& faumif v&lygonV wpenf t m; jzi h jrefmw& ½&myawmft rnfsm; onf pmay?
, Ob&sr& orll f jz p&yftr& rnf ES h quby&eoub& ½&myawmft rnfsm; onf vnf
jrefm&ompum; t o&t E&f; tac: ta0: rsm; ES h quby&eygonV

ppmwrf w&f jrefm&myawmft rnfsm; ull pmay? , Ob&sr& "av&h& p&h rsm; ES h
quby&wi fy rnf jz p&oub& b&ompum; z&zx& pnf; urf rsm;? teuft "y&h, f&v&quf
az&ma&qmi f rnf; vrf rsm; w&f yg c&f&x& avlv m o&h; rnf jz p&lygonV

1/ ½&myawmft [bnf

½&myawmft q&bnf&h jrefmvr&wll onf tpOf t quf v&u&qilurfo, fa&qmi f
usi fy&cy&uonf y&awmft rnfsm; ull q&lygonV jrefmjy&e&ft& web&t? uq&e? e, le? Ogq&
Ogac&gi? awm&ovif? o&wif&ur&w& web&qmi f rnf? ew&awmft jymo& wy&v& waygi f [li
12- v&mo&b&w&r&sv&fxm; &m jrefm&myawmft rnfsm; onf vnf 12- v&mo&Dt v&lluf
usi fyav&lygonV

, if&on jrefm&v&plq, ES& v& moly&awmft rnfsm; usi fy&cy&lyll ule&f&bmi fa&cw&E&ni f
pmq&lluf i&f&e&ri f&ll&du -

j jtwmweb&t? ES& O&banmi fa&? pmyav&e&it? yO&E&f&awmft&
pma&; w&ES& jrpf, ly&ll&? q&D&x&e&f&c&e& ux&e&ew&usi f?

* a' gu&f&vm? w&e&ly&garmu? jrefm&pm&xme/ y&ct&wu&ob&f

jritciitp&i? obitryh? *Molyll applusify? q, Eptv?
rswll&mody¹

[li uAsmvufijzi hrswlwrftwiclygonf

xllmumi h q, Ept&modt vlulusi fyonh jrefm&my&awmfrsm; u llunivdi f
webt;vwof obuleyB uqelvwof anmi&a&oeft; e, lefvwof pmjyetyB Ogqllvwof
OgqlyESH yO&ftcyB OgqbuetyuyvlyB Ogacgfvwof pma&wlyB awmbovitvwof
avjylyB odwifurwvwof rdxetyB qdrdxetyB weaqmi rlet;vwof weaqmi lwllyB
uxebuletyuyvlyB ewawmfvwof pmqlawmyB ewly&ZmyB jymollvwof
jritciitobilyB wylvwvwof xreyB rdxetyB waygitvwof waygityB olyhpwy&wllul
usityav&llmumif awllygonf

1? 1/ jrefm&my&awmfrsmESH , Obu&rbemutH

webt;vonf jrefm&my&awmfrsmESH yxro&qllvyifzponf/ jrefm&my&awmfrsmESH
webt;vqbnh aOg [m&rln xef,odctonlv [k t"ylyh, bu&amulyd ouwvbmom
]]umv}} rS qitoufmaom trnjzponf/² webt;vwof usityaomy&awmfrsmESH obulef
y&awmfrsmESH: twma&obily&awmfrsmESH/]lobulef [hom pum;onf ygVpum; ouE&A
ouwv pum; obulef rS qitoufvmjicit³ jzpfy& utajymifjicit [k t"ylyh, &ygonf

Epta [mituleqllr Eptopoll utajymifjicitfyifzponf/ jrefm&my&awmfrsmESH
Epta [mituleqllr Eptopoll utajymifonh txrttrsvftaejzih webt;vtc&ftcgwof
a&yuz&efupm; llunonh twmobulef&awmfrsmESH usityav&llbnf

uqelvonf jrefm&my&awmfrsmESH 'kvd ajrmulvzponf/]lu}} onf a& [k
t"ylyh, &jy&]]qes}} rln o&favmitjicit [k teu&ygonf/ xllmumi h uqelvwof
anmi&a&oeft; y&awmfrsmESH usityav&lllygonf/ b&am;avmit odwritom; zln; jri&omvzpf
onhtjiif b&am; y&awmfrsmESH aAm" anmi fyi fll jrwp&llb&am; ull yaZlonht xrttrsvfzih
a&oeft;avmit fav&lllygonf

jrefm&my&awmfrsmESH wwd ajrmulvrln e, lefvzponf/ yll&cw? tifOacw&ll
ausmupmwll eH le? e, le? eH&le? [k tr&tr& a& xll&llunonf/ aOg [m&vw&lye&ll
usrfjy/k&murl]]e&, k}} [hom ygVpum;rS e, lefvzponf [k qll&am; ygonf/ ⁴
e&, konf arxle&llmoll tac: ta0: wpr&lljzpfy& usm;r, llw&ll&om eu&v&llmoll [k
teu&ygonf/⁵ wptzele, lefvdi]]eyll bonf t&ftcgumv [k teu&jy&]], le}} yll bonf
, llus& p&us& 1/2 llus [k t"ylyh, &ygonf/ ⁶ rllpwi 1/2 ll&omumv [k owtrsvf
ac: qll&llrnjzponf/ e, lefv\y&awmfrsmESH]]pmawmfrsmESH pmjyety& jzponf/]]jrefm
ou&llZf 1100 - jynEpt omverifw&am;vulxur&ly& pmawmfrsmESH usity&llmumif

¹ zllvw&ll O&ll (1963)? 60/
² c&ll O&ll (1964)? 25/
³ -, if.-? 30/
⁴ -, if.-? 32/
⁵ -, if.-? 35/
⁶ zllvw&ll O&ll (1963)? 20/

jrefmES hitEG fwaom bmompum; rsm; wof Jysm; za, mitf} [k teufzof x; m; avkzbnf¹
Jod} \teufn obvni jci f; jzponf/ xhMumih jymolvonf ysm; za, mitf; pfi
t&qhv [kt"yih, f&v m; r; jzponf/

xlv&modum; qdES f; xlyfyd at; crfaom&modjzpojzih awmiobv, form; rsm;
tem, Muom tcefvjzponf/ obom xlv&modvof b&iNppbnfawm; rsm;
tvlyrsm; aomtcefvjzponf/ b&iwyravm; wof t; xto; jzih Munf; w; yravm; form; rsm; \
ppMuDcityac: jritcifobiyul qif, ifusityuygonf/ ritndifom;? ritajr;
rsm; ES f; wuGrS; MuD rwludppbaemywluDvvl p&ka&mu/2Mu; jyd ppDw; lvefqmrsm; jzpaom
c; yf; e; h; wluD oyl, ybn Owq; iMu; jyd ouq; h; &mw; yz; t; o; d; r; S "m;? v
av; jrm; ponf; wluD p; luD Mu; jyd eef; &i; j; y; f; wof p; f; &n; f; r; r; s; j; y; o; m; & y; gonf/ j; y; m; o; h;
v; w; d; f; j; r; i; f; c; i; f; o; b; i; ES hit w; l; q; i; f; i; f; o; b; i; f; y; r; s; m; u; l; w; p; f; y; h; i; w; n; f; u; s; i; f; y; a; v; h; z; u; y; gonf/

jrefm; yu^oeN 11-vajrmubnf wywlvjzponf/ xlv&modvof xef&nfrsm;
&cefvjzpf xef; v; sub; p; r; s; m; t; w; l; u; f; t; v; l; y; r; s; m; c; e; f; j; z; p; y; gonf/ awmiobv, form; MuD
rsm; onf ouMuDpyg; [lac: aom aumuMuDpyg; ay: cefvjzpf ai puav; rsm; 1/2 f; o; j; z; i; h
, m* y; r; s; m; qif, ifusityavh; uonf/ wywlv&wof , m* [lac: Muom xrelyrsm; r; s;
w; p; y; g; r; b; y; h; v; s; y; r; s; m; u; l; w; n; f; j; y; k; v; y; f; a; v; h; z; u; y; gonf²

rbylv; syul wywlvjynhaewof usityavh; uonf/ jrwpbnb&m; ociftm; tcrfrs
oubomap&ef 1/2 s; ftmeEmu 'lu#awmwiw; f; t; ay; j; c; i; f; u; l; u; s; r; f; *e; r; s; m; u; awD&ay onf/
xhMumih elbmxi; r; s; m; j; z; i; h b&m; u; l; &n; p; t; v; s' g; e; f; M; u; j; c; i; f; u; l; r; d; z; e; f; y; h; r; b; y; h; y; [k
ac: u; y; gonf/ r; d; z; e; f; y; h; t"yih, f; n; r; d; z; e; f; onf y; g; v; b; m; o; m; p; u; m; ; J; y; h; } r; s; q; i; f; o; u; f
v; m; o; n; h; a; o; g; [m; & j; z; p; o; n; f/ J; y; h; } onf b; e; f; w; e; c; h;? a; u; m; i; f; r; i; u; b; w; f; t; v; s; [k; t; e; u; &
y; gonf³ t; v; e; h; t; j; r; o; n; h; w; y; w; l; v; w; o; f; b; & m; ; p; i; r; s; m; a; 1/2 u; r; d; z; i; h? & [e; f; o; l; C; m; r; s; m; E; S; h
ouMuD 1/2 g; f; t; r; s; m; r; d; z; i; h; e; l; o; m; x; i; f;? r, f; r; s; (r; d; t; u; i; f;) p; o; n; f; w; l; u; l; b; & m; ; a; u; s; i; f; o; n; f
v; s' g; e; f; o; n; f; y; h; u; l; r; d; z; e; f; y; h; [k; a; c; j; c; i; f; j; z; p; o; n; f/ r; d; z; e; f; y; h; r; b; y; h; y; [l; i; o; h; i; f; o; j; z; i; h
ajymi; f; v; a; c; q; i; c; i; f; v; n; f; j; z; p; o; n; f/

jrefm; yu^oeN 12-clajrmuivrni wayg; i; f; v; jzponf/ jrefm; v; r; s; m; wof aemuq; h
v; v; n; f; j; z; p; o; n; f/ wayg; i; f; v; u; l; x; e; f; a; y; g; i; f; v; [l; v; n; f; a; c; : M; u; o; n; f/ ⁴ x; e; f; & n; f; u; s; i; f; u; b; o; m; v
jzponf/ x; e; f; z; y; i; f; & a; o; m; n; y; & n; E; S; h; x; e; f; r; y; i; f; & a; o; m; o; D; E; & n; i; w; l; u; l; a; y; g; i; f; p; y; u; d; c; u; f
o; j; z; i; h; x; e; f; a; y; g; i; f; v; [k; a; c; j; c; i; f; j; z; p; o; n; f/ ⁵ x; e; f; a; y; g; i; f; r; s; x; a; y; g; i; f;? w; a; y; g; i; f; [l; i; t; q; i; l; q; i; h
ajymi; f; v; v; m; j; c; i; f; j; z; p; o; n; f/

wayg; i; f; v; wof o; y; h; p; w; y; u; l; u; s; i; f; y; a; v; h; z; u; y; gonf/ o; y; h; p; w; y; u; l; b; n; f; n; i; o; c; h
a; o; m; i; f; & v; u; o; j; z; i; h; w; n; h; a; q; m; u; f; y; k; v; y; f; x; m; ; a; o; m; b; & m; ; a; p; w; l; u; l; o; c; h; p; w; l; [k; a; c; : y; gonf/
o; y; h; p; w; l; o; n; f; , m, w; n; x; m; ; u; l; u; g; h; o; m; b; & m; ; u; l; y; h; ; a; p; w; y; i; j; z; p; o; n; f/ o; y; h; p; w; l
w; n; & m; wof t; q; i; l; i; g; ; q; i; j; y; k; v; y; w; n; x; m; ; o; n; f/ j; r; i; f; r; & a; w; m; i; wof t; m; v; e; f; i; g; ; q; i; h; z; o; n; f; u; l
& n; 1/2 g; j; y; d; i; g; ; q; i; w; n; x; m; ; j; c; i; f; j; z; p; o; n; f/ , i; f; i; g; ; q; i; u; l; a; 1/2 j; y; m;? a; i; j; y; m;? a; 1/2 a; i; p; u; l

¹ -, if-? 59/
² ewh; s; l; (' *ef-)? 1967? 82/
³ [kvpe; l; (O; D-)? 1958? 65/
⁴ c; e; l; (O; D-)? 1968? 50/
⁵ c; e; l; (O; D)? (1964)? 52/

ponfzi hijkvlvluon/ rsm;aomtm;jzi hvG fuaom iSubaysmwfzihijkvlyluav on/ tmvli g; qilyth; terhitjrihpwDPhel vuf, m&pywtxm;&on/ xlaemuf oepibonbrsm; tjynboyxn&on/ wtkel uluim; ponfzih yaZmZG &mrsm;jzih jc, M\$ fjljyixm;jyDrStaeuzmwilvluon/1

ponfzih jrefm 12-v&modtvluf yawmftoDobusi fyMuyhrsm;ES h , Obausr laemubhrsm;onf pdvDi pm;zG faumi f;vSygon/

2/ twaA'ESht"yih, ftrstpm

twaA'onf teuft"yih, fuhvhwmaom ynm&yfwptczpfyD bmomaA' \ ynm&yfcG wptczpfygon/ ynm/2S ftcslu bmompum;ES h quobG EtlbrO tallumi f&mtm;vhuil teuft"yih, ftjzpf us, fus, fyefyel owrswluon/ tcslu teuf/2 (oabmvuPmjyteu)ubm teuf[kowrswluygon/ teuft"yih, (7)rst cfc; Etlfygon/ , ifwlrh -

- 1/ teuf/2 (oabmvuPmjyteu)
- 2/ *P&nfyteuf
- 3/ cpm;ryteuf
- 4/ vhrtajctaejyteuf
- 5/ 'elwhtteuf
- 6/ E\$zubhr;teuf
- 7/ tav;ay;teuf wljzpluygon/

1/ teuf/2 (oabmvuPmjyteu)

pum;vljzih &nhtfaomtnhtclhrsm; \ oabmvuPmrsm;uul tbd'mefteuf zG qlyhrstjzihzG qhbm teufzpygon/ teuf/2onf bmompum;jzih quobG &mwDf tcuftcsmuom teufzpon/ xlteurshuul ynwfteuf? o%yabzmteuf? orhteuf[li trst ac:luon/

2/ *P&nfyteuf

tnhtclwDf teuf/2[k cfc;owrswtxm;aom vuPmrsm;tjyif tjcm;*P&nfrsm;vnf rsm;pbh/2ygon/ tnhtclh *P&nfrsm;uul azmjyonhteufuul *P&nfyteuf[hc:on/ *P&nfyteuf[bnf acwft&vnfaumi f? , Obausrht&vnfaumi f? yk&vft&vnfaumi f, ajymi f;vlwvhaomoabm/2bnf

3/ cpm;ryteuf

1 ewh/2S? ('*k-f)? 1967? 28/

pum;vhwof xif[yaeom cpm;ruul cpm;rjyteuf[k: on/ ohef
ajmqhompum;wof ajmoNyf%wucpm;r? ajmolu emoltay:xm;onh oabmxm;
ajmoluajmaeonhtalumi f t&mtay:xm;onhoabmxm;wixif[yaeuf, ifwul
cpm;rjyteuf[k:ygon/ wpdqh emrism;wofvnt, cpm;rxif[yel[yg on/

4/ vritajctaejyteuf

tcspum;vhrsm;wof tohylowlN vritqihwefajymont&? quob[ri
yph tohy&me, y, ponh vritajctae trstul ohefajmqh onh pum;rs;wof
tohylowlN vritajctaersm; xif[yae ygon/ pteubabmul vritajctaej
teuf[k: on/

5/ 'elwteuf

pum;vhrsm; wquftohy[ci fji h&omteuful' elwteuf[k: on/

6/ Eptzubh teuf

teufwptckuyhom pum;vhrsm;wof teufwptckjih tohy[pof tjc; teuf
wptckyg ay: xufmvif xiteuful Eptzubh; teuf[k: on/

7/ tav;ay;teuf

pum;ajm&mwof pma&&mwof tav;xm;vbnhtcsuful xi 1/2n;atmi f
p0hajmqh&;om;jci fji h tav;ay; teuf ay: xufvmygon/

3/ jrefm&myawmtrnrsnull teuft "yih, fynm&xmi fSavlvnjci f

jrefm&myawmtrnrs; teuf web;v&mo wof usi fyonh ome yawmonf ygv pum;
]ouE? ouwpum;]omUE; wul jrefmrjyfyd]omUE; [k ajmi fvac: qh
xm;jci fjp on/ xalumi h ygv ouwvrsmaom ome f (utajmi fji f) [hom
pum;vEsh jrefmpum;]y; wul aygi fpyfyd]omUE; [k ac: qhxm;jci fjp on/
teuft "yih, ftm; jih Eptp utajmi f onh txrt rswjih usi fyonhyawm[k
teufojjih teufwptckijzpygon/ pum;v trstpm;t&]omUEsh y; 1/2lod
Eptckaygi f xm;aom pum;aygi f wptckijzpygon/

ome yawmud]a&obi y; [lvnt jrefmqefqefac: qh wvlygon/ jrefm pum;
]a&? ygv pum;]obm, } rsvaomobi? jrefmpum;]y; paom 1/2lod rsm;
aygi fpyaeon pum;aygi f wptckijzpyd teufwptckvnt jzpygon/

uqelvwof usi fyonh]anmi h&oe f} yawmtrnwlvnt anmi f
(emr^ 1/2lod)? a& (emr^ 1/2lod) Esh oef (Mud m^ 1/2lod) wul aygi fpyftohy/xm; onh
pum;aygi f trstpm;wptckijzpygon/ jrwpob&m;y; awmtrm aAm' anmi f iul
&nptjy anmi h&oe f avmi f onhy [homteuful azma qmi h eojjih teuft "yih, f
trstpm;t& teufwptckijzpygon/

e, lfvwof usi fyonhyawmtrnrs pma wmyelyzpon/ , iftrni
aog[m&ul avlv m&mwoflvnt, pm (emr^ 1/2lod)? awm (ypint^ 1/2lod)? jef (Mud m^
1/2lod) Esh y; (emr^ 1/2lod) tpwft yf rsm; aygi fpyfyg oi h eonh pum;a&mwptckij
zpon/ teuft "yih, ftrstpm;t&vnt teufwptckijzpygon/

Ogq\y\awm\zpaom }Ogq\y\ trnbnf }Ogq} aex\jci\ [bom ygVd pum;v\rsqifou\mon\ Og (emr\^1/2ky\ob)? q\ (Mud m^1/2ky\ob)? y\ (emr\^1/2ky\ob) w\ ayg\tpyxm;onh pum;ayg\fwpc\y\jzpb\on\ teuft"y\h, ft&vnf & [ef,o\cm awm\rs; Ogq\ Oguy\jci\ul w\1/2u&n\h\ē;azmfyonh teu\1/2pum;v\wpc\y\jzpb\on\

Ogacg\fvw\ us\fyonh }pma&w\h\y\ onf jrefmpum; pma&w\h (emr\ pum;ayg\f) ES h r\ (emr\pum;1/2h)w\ ayg\tpyxm;aom pum;ayg\fwpc\y\jzpb\on\ & [ef,o\cmw\ trn\emrrs;a&;x\hxm;aom r\w\h\sm;ul &n\p\ac:a0:xm;jci\jzpb\ojzi h teu\1/2yi jzplygon\

}pma&w\h [hompum;ul c\jcrf\un\fv\i\pm(emr\^1/2ky\ob)? a&;(Mud m^1/2ky\ob) ES h w\emr\^1/2ky\ob)w\ ayg\tpyxm;ayg\oi\faealumi\ aw\&ygon\ teuft"y\h, ftr\st\tpm; t& teu\1/2wpc\y\jzpb\on\

awm\ovi\fvw\fav\y\h\y\ac: yef,v\bbi\y\ES h opq\iy\w\ us\fyav\h\1/2ygon\ opq\iy\onf , cktcg rus\fyawm\alumi\ o&on\

av\y\h\y\trnbnf av\ (emr\^1/2ky\ob)? j\h\i (Mud m^1/2ky\ob)ES h y\ (emr\^1/2ky\ob) ayg\tpyxm;jci\jzpb\on\ teuft"y\h, ftr\st\tpm;t& teu\1/2wpc\y\jzpb\on\

av\y\h\y\ul yef,v\bbi\y\ [kvnf ac:on\ yef,v\bbi\y\trn\ul pum;v\ z\h\h\& c\jcrf\p\w\jzml\un\fygu yef (emr\^1/2ky\ob)? vk (Mud m^1/2ky\ob)? ES h yg\vbom pum; }obm, } r\ vmaomobif (emr\^1/2ky\ob) w\ul ayg\tpyxm;jci\ jzpb\on\ yg\oi\faom 1/2y&i\ftr\st\tpm;w\h\& pum;ayg\fwpc\jzpa\lumi\ aw\&ygon\ teuft"y\h, ftr\st\tpm;t& w\ipm;teu\wpc\y\jzpb\on\

o\w\i\fu\rv\fvw\ r\h\ē\y\ul us\fyav\h\ygon\ r\h\ē\y\trnbnf jrefmbom pum;ppp\y\jzpb\on\ r\ (emr\^1/2ky\ob)? x\ē\ (Mud m^1/2ky\ob)ES h y\ (emr\^1/2ky\ob)w\ul ayg\tpyxm;jci\jzpb\on\ yg\oi\faom 1/2y&i\ftr\st\tpm;w\h\& pum;ayg\fwpc\y\jzpb\on\ teuft"y\h, ftr\st\tpm;t& teu\1/2wpc\y\jzpb\on\

o\w\i\fu\rv\y\awm\ul a\1/2su jri\fr\y\bbi\ [kvnf ac:lunon\ , i\pum; v\ul c\jcrf\p\w\jzml\un\fygu r\ (emr\^1/2ky\ob) ES h yg\vpum; ar\1/2rs qifou\vmaom jri\fr\ē\ (emr\^1/2ky\ob)w\ul ayg\tpyxm;jci\jzpb\ojzi h pum;ayg\fwpc\ [k ow\rs\vf E\h\ygrn\ teuft"y\h, ft&vnf jri\fr\ē\awm\ixul w\m\ow\bmew\jyn\rs jrwp\h\b&m; qifou\mon\h\ x\h\tr\svft\jzpf q\h\y\azmf\jci\ul &n\h\ē\jci\jzpb\ojzi h w\ipm;teu\ wpc\y\jzplygon\

w\ēaqmi\ref\fvw\ us\fyonh w\ēaqmi\w\h\y\awm\trnbn\vnf jrefmqe\ p\w\di\pm;z\ē\ h\umi\fygon\ }w\ēaqmi\w\h\ onf A [DP\y\ob\jzpfy\ q\h\ē\vf\ awm\yon\ [k teu\&ygon\ }w\h\ on\vnf 1/2ky\ob\1/2y&i\jzpfy\ tc\stcgumv [k teu\&ygon\ x\h\lumi\h w\ēaqmi\w\h\y\ trn\ul\h\vm\vi\ w\ēaqmi\ (emr\^1/2ky\ob)? w\h\ (emr\^1/2ky\ob) ES h y\ (emr\^1/2ky\ob)w\ ayg\tpyxm;aom pum;ayg\fwpc\jzpb\on\ teuft"y\h, ftr\st\tpm;t& teu\1/2wpc\y\jzpb\on\

w\ēaqmi\ref\fvw\ us\fyonh w\ēaqmi\ref\fv\ &mod\wpc\h\h\ ux\ē\y\jzpb\on\ & [ef,o\cmw\ul ux\ē\ou\ē\qu\uy\y\azm\on\h\y\y\jzplygon\ }ux\ē\y\ \trn\h\h

ygVbompum; Juxē} uJrefmrjyKxm; onh Juxē}(emr^{1/2}lyto) ES h yG (emr^{1/2}lyto)
pum; vhwuUaygi fpyKxm; onpum; aygi fwpckyi jzplygon/

uxēbouēfuyvSjci f uU & n h ēf; ac: qKxm; onh y h w m f t r n j z p l o n / x h M u m i h
teuft "yūh, ftrstpm; t& teul^{1/2}wpckyi jzplygon/

ewāwmfvwGf usifyaomy h w m f t r n j z p l o n / p m q h w m f t r n i u l
pum; vhwuUaygi fpyKxm; onpum; aygi fwpckyi jzplygon/ (emr^{1/2}lyto) ES h qU (Mud m) aygi f x m ; o n h
1/2lyto) pum; vhwuUaygi fpyKxm; onpum; aygi fwpckyi jzplygon/ jawm; onf M u M u , j r i f r w r i u l u U f p m ; j y l o n t y p o n f p u m ; v h
1/2lyto) jzplygon/ JyG onf emr^{1/2}lyto) pum; vhwuUaygi fpyKxm; onpum; aygi fwpckyi jzplygon/ x h M u m i h j p m q h w m f t r n i u l
onpum; a&mwpclyi jzplygon/ teuft "yūh, ftrstpm; t& teul^{1/2}lyi jzplygon/

a^{1/2}Su ewāwmfvwGf qizrfy usifyav^{1/2}on/ JqizrfyG trniu h v h w m v G f
qif (emr^{1/2}lyto)? zrf (Mud m^{1/2}lyto)? yG (emr^{1/2}lyto) w l z i h z l o n f x m ; a o m
pum; aygi f y i j z p l y g o n / t e u f t r s t p m ; t & t e u l ^{1/2} w p c k y i j z p l y g o n /

jymolwGf usifyon h w m f t r n j z p l o n / j r i f c i f o b i y G j z p l o n / j r i f c i o b i y U l l
pum; vhwuUaygi fpyKxm; onpum; aygi fwpckyi jzplygon/ (emr^{1/2}lyto)? ci f (Mud m^{1/2}lyto) ES h y G v p u m ;
J o b m , } r S q i f o u f v m a o m a r G p m ; p u m ; v h J o b i } (e m r ^{1/2} l y t o) w u l l a y g i f p y
x m ; j c i f j z p l o n / x h M u m i h j r i f c i f o b i y G t r n o n f p u m ; a y g i f w p c k y i j z p l o n /
teuft "yūh, ftrstpm; t& teul^{1/2}wpckyi jzplygon/

wyUwV \ y h w m f t r n j z p l o n / x r e f x r E S ; a c : , m * l y h w m f z p l o n / x r e b n f x r i f E a c :
aumufS f q e l u l o r o t h ; a t m i f w p e n f J E S o h ; a t m i f j y k v l y & a o m
& m o d t p m ; t p m w p r s t j z p l o n / x r e f x r i f E S u l p u m ; v h w u U a y g i f p y f y d J y G (e m r ^{1/2} l y t o) u l l x y q i h
J x r i f } (e m r ^{1/2} l y t o) E S h J E S (M u d m ^{1/2} l y t o) w u l l a y g i f p y f y d J y G (e m r ^{1/2} l y t o) u l l x y q i h
aygi fpyG ac: qKxm; jci f jzplygon/ pum; vhwuUaygi fpyKxm; onpum; aygi fwpckyi jzplygon/ JyG (emr^{1/2}lyto) ul l x y q i h
teuft "yūh, ftrstpm; t& teul^{1/2} [kowfSwEh f y g o n /

, m * l y G [k a c : q K c i f r o v n f x r E S u l y i f & n h ē f ; o n h y g v p u m ; J , m * l
(emr^{1/2}lyto) jzi hwz uft "yūh, tG f q K m ; j c i f y i j z p l o n /

wyUwVwGf usifyon h r z l e f y a c : r d y h y o n f j r e r m p u m ; J r d } (e m r ^{1/2} l y t o)
E S h y G v o u i v r s m a o m J y h ^ y i P } u l l j r e r m r j y l a r G p m ; x m ; o n h J z l e f o l r [k v i y h
(emr^{1/2}lyto) w u l l a y g i f p y a c : q K m ; j c i f j z p l o n / p u m ; v h t r s t p m ; t & p u m ; a y g i f
jzplyd teuft "yūh, ftrstpm; t& * P & n j y t e u l [k o w f S w E h f y g r n /

waygi f v \ y h w m f t r n j z p l o n / o j z i h a p w d y k P h e f y k v l y f a z m o n h
y j z p l o n / J o l y l o n f y k m ; a o m o l [k t e u & r n h e m r O d o o e y g a o m e m r p u m ;
aygi fwpckjzplygon/ z l o n f y h t & o l (e m r ^{1/2} l y t o) E S h y h (M u d m ^{1/2} l y t o) w u l l
aygi fpyKxm; jci f jzplygon/ J a p w d o n f y g v p u m ; J a p w d } r s m a o m (e m r ^{1/2} l y t o)
y i j z p l o n / x h M u m i h J o l y l o p w d t r n o n f p u m ; a y g i f w p c k j z p l y d t e u l ^{1/2} v n f
jzplygon/

Jcll hloytsuf

Jrefmvrstwl q, ES&moJawmfrsonf pmay, Ohausri orlfaemutcl
rsqES fqupyfyd jzpxēfay:ayguvmjci f y i j z p l o n / A R O m o m u l o u D i f , M u n f r S

wpfi h bmoma&ES hqupyhaeom y&rfobiftr&rdul vucl usifyvmlujicyif jzponf

AR bmonESH h quEG haeomy&rfobiftr&tjiif tpOft vml'avb&h&h&hESH tnd usiyaom y&rfobiftr&tjymul/nfaw&ayonf AR bmonESH h quEG f aeonh y&wnfr&tjzpf uq&lvw&fusiyonh annih&o&efy& e, &lvw&fusiyonh pnjyey& Ogq&lvw&fusiyonh Ogq&lvw&fusiyonh Oqacgivw&fusiyonh pma&w&h&ty& olvif&lvw&fusiyonh q&drif&lvw&fusiyonh we&qmif&lvw&fusiyonh ux&lvw&fusiyonh wy&lvw&fusiyonh r&dz&lvw&fusiyonh waygif&lvw&fusiyonh o&lvw&fusiyonh aw&ay onf

tpOft vml'avb&h&h&hESH tnd usiyav&lvw&fusiyonh y&wnfr&tjzpf we&lvw&fusiyonh usiyaom o&lvw&fusiyonh aw&ayonh av&lvw&fusiyonh ew&lvw&fusiyonh pmaq&lvw&fusiyonh jym&lvw&fusiyonh jrif&lvw&fusiyonh wy&lvw&fusiyonh usiyaom wr&lvw&fusiyonh aw&ayonf

jref&lvw&fusiyonh y&wnfr&tjzpf av&lvw&fusiyonh y&lvw&fusiyonh ar&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh jz&lvw&fusiyonh aygif&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh monh o&lvw&fusiyonh Ogq&lvw&fusiyonh q&drif&lvw&fusiyonh ux&lvw&fusiyonh r&dz&lvw&fusiyonh o&lvw&fusiyonh jrif&lvw&fusiyonh aw&ayonh annih&o&efy& pnjyey& pma&w&h&ty& av&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh pmaq&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh jref&lvw&fusiyonh o&lvw&fusiyonh oubuz&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh monh y&wnfr&tjzpf ul/nf aw&ayonf

jref&lvw&fusiyonh y&wnfr&tjzpf pum&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh mif&lvw&fusiyonh &lvw&fusiyonh ul/nf y&lvw&fusiyonh o&lvw&fusiyonh aygif&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh monh pum&lvw&fusiyonh aygif&lvw&fusiyonh jz&lvw&fusiyonh p&lvw&fusiyonh aw&ayonf

teuft "y&lvw&fusiyonh, v&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh mif&lvw&fusiyonh &lvw&fusiyonh ul/nf teuft wif&lvw&fusiyonh p&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh *P&lvw&fusiyonh jz&lvw&fusiyonh teuft r&lvw&fusiyonh p&lvw&fusiyonh o&lvw&fusiyonh aw&ayonf

edh

p&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh jref&lvw&fusiyonh y&wnfr&tjzpf pum&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh mif&lvw&fusiyonh &lvw&fusiyonh ul/nf teuft t "y&lvw&fusiyonh, v&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh mif&lvw&fusiyonh &lvw&fusiyonh ul/nf av&lvw&fusiyonh wif&lvw&fusiyonh jz&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh bl&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh mif&lvw&fusiyonh p&lvw&fusiyonh ay, O&lvw&fusiyonh h&lvw&fusiyonh a&lvw&fusiyonh em&lvw&fusiyonh ul/nf &lvw&fusiyonh aw&ayonh jz&lvw&fusiyonh pum&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh mif&lvw&fusiyonh &lvw&fusiyonh ul/nf taj&lvw&fusiyonh c&lvw&fusiyonh jz&lvw&fusiyonh pum&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh mif&lvw&fusiyonh &lvw&fusiyonh ul/nf teuft "y&lvw&fusiyonh, v&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh mif&lvw&fusiyonh &lvw&fusiyonh ul/nf az&lvw&fusiyonh n&lvw&fusiyonh wif&lvw&fusiyonh jz&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh my&lvw&fusiyonh jref&lvw&fusiyonh O&lvw&fusiyonh h&lvw&fusiyonh a&lvw&fusiyonh em&lvw&fusiyonh ul/nf jz&lvw&fusiyonh pum&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh mif&lvw&fusiyonh &lvw&fusiyonh ul/nf tax&lvw&fusiyonh muft&lvw&fusiyonh y&lvw&fusiyonh jz&lvw&fusiyonh p&lvw&fusiyonh apr&lvw&fusiyonh n&lvw&fusiyonh k , l&lvw&fusiyonh q&lvw&fusiyonh

ur&lvw&fusiyonh f&lvw&fusiyonh ul/nf

cif&lvw&fusiyonh i&lvw&fusiyonh p&lvw&fusiyonh ("E&lvw&fusiyonh jz&lvw&fusiyonh l)/ v&lvw&fusiyonh u&lvw&fusiyonh b&lvw&fusiyonh ut&lvw&fusiyonh wa&lvw&fusiyonh A'ed&lvw&fusiyonh gef&lvw&fusiyonh / &lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l
c&lvw&fusiyonh s&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l O&lvw&fusiyonh p&lvw&fusiyonh av&lvw&fusiyonh b&lvw&fusiyonh i&lvw&fusiyonh t&lvw&fusiyonh w&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l 0&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l (1964)/ a&lvw&fusiyonh O&lvw&fusiyonh g&lvw&fusiyonh [n&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh w&lvw&fusiyonh -j&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l] &lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l p&lvw&fusiyonh may&lvw&fusiyonh b&lvw&fusiyonh P&lvw&fusiyonh l&lvw&fusiyonh l
z&lvw&fusiyonh h&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh w&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l O&lvw&fusiyonh p&lvw&fusiyonh (1958)/ j&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh f&lvw&fusiyonh pum&lvw&fusiyonh t&lvw&fusiyonh z&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l&lvw&fusiyonh l &lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l y&lvw&fusiyonh n&lvw&fusiyonh me&lvw&fusiyonh E&lvw&fusiyonh y&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l
z&lvw&fusiyonh h&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh w&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l O&lvw&fusiyonh p&lvw&fusiyonh (1963)/ j&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh f&lvw&fusiyonh m&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh t&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh n&lvw&fusiyonh f&lvw&fusiyonh m&lvw&fusiyonh l &lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l y&lvw&fusiyonh n&lvw&fusiyonh me&lvw&fusiyonh E&lvw&fusiyonh y&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l
ew&lvw&fusiyonh l&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l ' *e&lvw&fusiyonh l (1967)/ p&lvw&fusiyonh may&lvw&fusiyonh O&lvw&fusiyonh w&lvw&fusiyonh q&lvw&fusiyonh h&lvw&fusiyonh t&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh s&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh i&lvw&fusiyonh 5? &lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l p&lvw&fusiyonh may&lvw&fusiyonh A&lvw&fusiyonh d&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l
j&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh f&lvw&fusiyonh pum&lvw&fusiyonh t&lvw&fusiyonh z&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l (2016)/ j&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh f&lvw&fusiyonh m&lvw&fusiyonh t&lvw&fusiyonh b&lvw&fusiyonh d&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l &lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l j&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh f&lvw&fusiyonh m&lvw&fusiyonh o&lvw&fusiyonh m&lvw&fusiyonh pum&lvw&fusiyonh O&lvw&fusiyonh p&lvw&fusiyonh x&lvw&fusiyonh m&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l
[k&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l O&lvw&fusiyonh p&lvw&fusiyonh (1958)/ y&lvw&fusiyonh v&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh O&lvw&fusiyonh h&lvw&fusiyonh o&lvw&fusiyonh m&lvw&fusiyonh a&lvw&fusiyonh c&lvw&fusiyonh :y&lvw&fusiyonh g&lvw&fusiyonh /j&lvw&fusiyonh r&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh f&lvw&fusiyonh m&lvw&fusiyonh t&lvw&fusiyonh b&lvw&fusiyonh d&lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l &lvw&fusiyonh e&lvw&fusiyonh l